

Location

Göteborg, Sweden

Innovation

SLAMD

Partners

BAM

TUB

Chalmers University

Trollhättan Minerals

SUMMARY OF SCOPE AND GOALS

This study is an exploration of how SLAMD can help shorten the experimental time of developing new recipes with alternative binders from CDW (glass and concrete) for new concrete production. The expected outcomes are SLAMD could be able to suggest and predict recipes that fulfill the requirement (compressive strength).

DATA TYPES, TOOLS, REPOSITORIES, URLS

slamd-demo.herokuapp.com/

KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

- › Compressive strength = 30 MPa
- › Cement replacement rate of at least 30%
- › Number of recipes which reach 30 MPa

CONTACTS

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IMPACT

LOW

Techno-Economic Impact

LOW

Societal Impact

LOW

Scientific Impact